

Electron Molecule Bonding Fabricator

With electrical field force molecule and atoms are arrange in specific required pattern and fabricator is connected to simulators for design of products with any design and atomic composition. The Project is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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Overview

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The physical ~~environmental~~ system will influence during their development and formation. More insight will be made information regarding their potential ~~design~~ ~~under~~ technical data and physical characteristics within this...

